

EXPLORING THE EFFECT OF AUDITOR'S INDEPENDENCE ON EARNINGS MANAGEMENT OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Auditor are expected to carry out audit functions to critically review a firms financial statements to ascertain if the financial statements are free from errors or manipulations. This study examined the effect of auditors' independence on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of auditor's tenure, audit fee and auditor's status on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria from 2012 to 2023. The secondary data were analysed using descriptive statistics and correlation matrix. The hypotheses were tested using fixed panel regression. The result obtained shows that audit fee has significant negative effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Auditor's tenure and status have an insignificant effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study concludes that higher auditor fees typically result in fewer discretionary accruals in banks due to improved audit quality, higher auditor vigilance, and regulatory compliance. The finding suggests that mandatory audit firm tenure policies may not be necessary if other mechanisms, such as robust regulatory environments, auditor specialization, and effective audit committees, are in place to ensure audit quality. The finding suggests that, in the context of banks, auditor status alone may not be a decisive factor in mitigating discretionary accruals. This could be due to the unique complexities and regulatory environments of the banking industry, which might limit the auditor's ability to detect or influence earnings management practices. The study, therefore, recommends that banks should avoid paying too low audit costs, which could lower the quality of the audit, and instead pay prices that reflect the complexity of their financial processes.

Keywords: Auditors Independence, Audit Fees, Audit Status, Audit Tenure, Earnings Management.

1. INTRODUCTION

The surge in worldwide accounting scandals has highlighted flaws in the integrity of financial reporting. Ignoring the gravity of the situation may lead shareholders and investors to lose faith and confidence, not only in the reliability of the company's financial statements but also in the accounting profession. Auditors are expected to provide better assurance of detecting earnings management by enhancing the reliability of financial reports. The main reason behind the use of earnings management by the management of a company is to improve the financial reporting quality of the company. Rahman et al. (2023) argued that analysts can assess a company's performance and future prospects using the information provided by high-quality financial reporting. Inaccurate, deceptive, or incomplete information can be found in poor or low-quality financial reporting. Kantudu and Alhassan (2022) opined that convergence and harmonization of accounting standards, economic crises, an increase in disclosure requirements, and other

reasons have led to an excessive emphasis on financial reporting.

Audit independence refers to the ability of the external auditor to act with integrity and impartiality during his/her auditing functions (Akpom & Dimkpah, 2013). Auditors' independence plays a major role in auditing and is a major concern in the auditing profession. Auditor independence encompasses both the firm engaged to perform external audits and the individual auditors who conduct the audit. Auditor independence ensures that the internal or external auditor from parties who might have a financial interest in the company are being audited. Integrity and objectivity are necessary for independence in the auditing process. Okegbe et al. (2019) argued that an auditor's independence describes an auditor's unbiased attitude in making decisions throughout the audit and financial reporting process. The main objective of an audit is to ensure that the financial statements provide a true and fair view and that the information in the audited financial statement can be used to make financial decisions. This objective will not be met if users of the audit report believe that the auditor may have been influenced by other parties, more specifically, company managers/directors, or by conflict. In addition, auditor independence is the most important factor in establishing the credibility of the audit opinion (Lokman & Bakri, 2020). If at any point in time, there was a threat to the auditor's independence during the audit process, it could have a huge impact on the quality of the audited financial statement. Ezuwore and Agbo (2020) assert that the objective of an audit is to increase the credibility of financial statements by giving reasonable assurance in writing from an independent source that they provide a true and fair picture in compliance with an accounting standard. This study proxies auditors' independence as audit fees, tenure and status.

Prior studies argue that audit fees is a significant factor for audit quality and thus enhance the financial reporting quality of firms by detecting the level of earnings management (DeFond & Zhang, 2014; Gaynor et al., 2016; Mesbah & Ramadan, 2022). This is because audit fees is assumed to accelerate audit efforts, which is associated to greater audit coverage and thus leads to better financial reporting quality (DeFond & Zhang, 2014; Molly & Mercer, 2016; Gaynor et al., 2016; Bala et al., 2018). While the determinants of audit fees are not new in literature, the significance of pricing audit fees within a bank's developing country context is limited. Therefore, this study examines how the audit fee paid by a firm affects earnings management in the firm's financial report in commercial in Nigeria.

Debates on audit tenure arise from the assumption that the length of the relationship between the external auditor and the client may lead to an intentional act of overlooking or inability to detect earnings management in the company's financial statements. This assumption is at the root of most of the debates on audit tenure. In this regard, the evidence presented in the previous research is mixed. A lengthy audit tenure may result in less independence and professional care being provided. Audit tenure is the length of time the auditor has examined a company. A shorter audit tenure, on the other hand, indicates that the auditors have less knowledge about the client, which may lead to a lower-quality audit. Long audit tenure may increase the knowledge about the client's internal operations, but the downside is that the auditor's independence may be compromised (Islam, 2016; Feleke, 2017). The clients change their auditors for many reasons, one of which is to obtain a reduced audit fee from a new auditor as

the new auditor may offer services at a discount to win a new client (Oladipupo & Emina, 2016). There is a mandatory law on companies as regards rotation of auditors. Changing audit firms regularly is part of a practice known as mandatory audit firm rotation. The goal of this practice is to prevent accounting fraud and misstatements by severing intimate ties between auditing firms and their customers (Kalabeke et al., 2019). Previous study shows that voluntary change of auditors is frequently linked to audit failures like fraud, financial distress, shareholder's discretion and auditor ineffectiveness (Malik et al., 2017). In addition, prior studies (Onyabe et al., 2019; Dijeh et al., 2022; Mesbah & Ramadan, 2022) claimed that long auditor tenure negatively affect audit quality, weaken auditor's independence and objectivity and lack of auditor's independence would encourage earnings management and creative accounting practices, because due to longer auditor tenure the auditors are closely linked to the management. Therefore, protect the stakes of management instead of stakeholders, whilst prior studies (Olaoye et al., 2019; Lambe et al., 2021; Olurankise & Ojo, 2022) link long tenure of an audit firm to the independence of the auditor. This dichotomy calls for further research on the effect of audit tenure on earnings management.

Auditor's status is a situation of categorizing external auditors into big four and non-big four audit firms. The Big 4 audit firms are thought to be large audit firms with very large human and financial resources to prosecute any audit assignment given to it by the client. Because of the availability of resources to the big four audit firms against the non-big four audit firms, literature had established link between the two variables thus; Daferighe and George (2020) affirms that audit exercise engaged by the big four would increase the quality of financial report and that the auditor would be able to detect earnings management in the financial report. The Big 4 auditors, such as Delliotte, PWC, KPMG, and EY, over the years have earned a reputation in providing quality audit services and are expected to perform a high-quality audit coherently to avoid audit failure because these firms will be on a high risk, losing clients as well as high audit fees. Various studies agree that Big 4 auditors are considered to provide a higher audit quality than non-Big 4 auditors.

Some researchers (Braam et al., 2015; Abosedra & Sita, 2018; Lopes, 2018; Mesbah & Ramadan, 2022) argue that when the risk of detecting earnings management increases, then firms are more inclined to adopt a less detectable earnings management strategy. Therefore, it is expected that firms audited by Big 4 auditors are likely to get less involved in determining the extent of discretionary accruals. Others argue that Otuya (2019), the big 4 audit firms, has a significant negative relationship with earnings management. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the effect of Big 4 audit firms on earnings management in commercial banks in Nigeria.

In addition, prior studies on auditor independence and earnings management focused on different sectors of the economy. For example, Ibrahim (2017) study focused on consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Olaoye et al. (2019) and Otuya (2019) examined the impact of the independence of auditors on the reliability of financial report on manufacturing companies in Nigeria. While Lambe et al. (2021) focused on listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. These studies' findings cannot be generalized to banks in Nigeria. Also, prior studies on auditor

independence and earnings management on banks in Nigeria have a period gap. For example, Dabor and Dabor (2015) study cover the period from 2006 and 2014. Onyabe et al., (2019) study covers the period 2007 to 2016. Oyebamiji (2022) study covered the period from 2008 to 2018. Amahalu and Obi (2020) focused on conglomerates in Nigeria. Ezuwore and Elias (2020) conducted a survey on banks in Enugu state. The period gaps observed in this study call for further research to extend the scope to the period ending in 2022.

Prior studies have adopted several proxies as a measure of earnings management. Otuya et al., (2017), Francis and Wang (2008), Carey and Simnett (2006) and Francis and Krishman (1999) used Discretionary Accruals (DACC). DeFond and Park (2001) also adopted abnormal working capital accrual as a measure of audit quality. This study adopts DACC as a measure of earnings management. DACC has been adjudged as a superior technique to determine the level of earnings management and, by extension, audit quality. Based on the DACC view, high-income smoothing/earnings management reduces the quality of financial reports. The implication is that higher DACC creates a greater distance between the true state of affairs (financial performance) and the results shown in the financial statements.

Based on the above stated gaps, this study seeks to explore the effect of auditors' independence, which is proxy by auditors' fees, tenure and status on earnings management as discretionary accruals in commercial in Nigeria. For this study, we want to consider the effect of auditor's independence on earnings management of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. Commercial banks are one of the operational financial sectors in Nigeria, and as such, there are lots of regulations put in place to guide their operations and financial procedures as well as their financial reporting. This study aims at identifying the impact of auditor's independence (audit tenure, audit fee, auditor's status and firm size) on determining the quality of their financial reports using the discretionary accrual model. This study is motivated by the researcher's opinion that auditors' independence does not affect earnings management, while others found out that auditor's independence might, to a small extent, have an impact on the financial report of an organization. This study is carried out to examine the impact of an auditor's independence on earnings management of some quoted commercial banks in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Several theories have been identified to explain the nexus between auditors' independence and earnings management. They include the agency theory, stakeholders theory and stewardship theory. However, this study is hinged in the agency theory developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976), which explores the conflict between owners and managers, which is one of the main reasons for demanding an audit. Auditors act as agents to principals when performing an audit, and this relationship therefore brings with it similar concerns about trust and confidence as the director-shareholder relationship, prompting questions about who is auditing the auditor. The Agency Theory is anchored on the basis that there exists an agency connection in which the owners of the firm assign responsibilities to the managers. This leads to the sharing of risks, which also gives rise to conflict of interest between the two parties. Managers are reputed to be motivated by self-interest rather than the need to maximize shareholders' wealth. The

principal agent contrasting interest is demonstrated in this concept, where owners (principal) nurse reasons not to have faith in their managers (agents) because of asymmetries of information and contrasting concerns (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Information asymmetry is concerned with situations whereby one party is judged to have more information than the other. In their confirmation of the validity of the financial statements, external auditors play an essential part in reducing this information asymmetry. An important postulation surrounding the agency theory is that the auditor is viewed as independent and, hence is expected to provide an independent opinion. Therefore, external auditors as a third party, are expected to bring into line management interests with shareholders and to let shareholders measure the conduct of their managers and reinforce confidence in management. Therefore, this study is hinged on the agency theory to explain the effect of auditor independence on the quality of financial reports.

Auditors Independence

Bahram (2007) defined auditor's independence as the ability of the auditor to maintain an objective and impartial mental attitude throughout an audit. In another vein, Arens et al. (2014) defined audit independence as requiring an attitude of responsibility that is separate from the client's interest; the auditor maintains an attitude of healthy professional skepticism. They explained that the independence of the auditor can be viewed from two perspectives, namely, independence in mind and independence in appearance. Arens et al. (2014) explain that independence entails an attitude of a sense of obligation distinct from the client's interest. Independence encourages the external auditor to display a position of healthy professional incredulity. Auditors independence is proxy as auditors fees, tenure and status.

Earnings Management

Earnings management refers to a company's intentional use of accounting techniques to improve the appearance of its financial statements. When a company feels pressured to manipulate earnings to meet a predetermined goal, earnings management may occur. Earnings management is the management discretion of external financial reports within GAAP, through which some contract deficiencies are exploited, the bounded rationalities of stakeholders, as well as market information asymmetry, by some economic decisions or changing the accounting treatment or other complex methods (El Diri, 2017). Earnings management is accrual management, which means using accruals to achieve a pre-determined goal (Goel, 2016). Earnings management is the intentional manipulation of financial statements by managers driven by various purposes (Ruiz, 2016).

In this study, earnings management is proxied by discretionary accruals measured using the Modified Jones model because it is more powerful in revealing the discretionary accruals than the original Jones model (Dechow et al. 1995). The decision to use discretionary accruals as the proxy for earnings management stems from the various benefits. First, it is an important factor in assessing the level of earnings increase which has been carried out by the management, and second, it will make our tests more reliable because the proxies will be responding specifically to the firm's reporting incentives and discretion. Earnings management happens when the managers manipulate the financial statements for their interests, and it is one of the main

concerns in examining the financial health of companies to indicate the level of reliability of reported earnings (Usman, 2013). El Diri (2018) believed that earnings management may negatively affect the financial reporting quality, as it is the act of overcasting financial reports made for external stakeholders and it is used by the management to tamper the firm's income to go in parallel with the firm's goals and this manipulation can hurt the quality of information given to investors and as the entity engages more in earnings management, the financial reporting quality of these entities will be adversely affected. Prior studies have adopted a number of proxies as a measure of earnings management. Otuya et al. (2017), Francis and Wang (2008), Carey and Simnett (2006) and Francis and Krishnan (1999) used Discretionary Accruals (DACC). DeFond and Park (2001) also adopted abnormal working capital accrual as a measure of audit quality. This study adopts DACC as a measure of earnings management. DACC has been adjudged as a superior technique to determine the level of earnings management and by extension, audit quality. Based on the DACC view, earnings management reduces the quality of financial reports. The implication is that higher DACC creates a greater distance between the true state of affairs (financial performance) and the results shown in the financial statements.

Auditors Fees and Earnings Management

Herath and Pradier (2018) defined audit fees as the amount charged to a client to conduct specific services by the accountant. The fee may vary by size or based on the type of service provided, but there have been many questions from researchers whether it affects audit quality. The amount of the audit fee can vary depending on the assignment risk, the service complexity, the level of expertise required, the cost structure of the Public Accountant Firm and other professional considerations. Oyetunji et al. (2022) defined audit fees as the amount auditors are paid for their professional services, which is determined by elements such as the complexity of the services and the level of experience among others.

Prior empirical studies have explored the effect of auditors' independence on earnings management. The findings differ, cutting across different sectors and geographical locations. For example, in Nigeria, Akanbi et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between the characteristics of an audit committee and the quality of financial reporting at a selection of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria from 2008 - 2019. The audit fee does not have a significant relationship with the quality of the financial reports. This claim was supported by Ibrahim (2017) study that found that audit fees have no significant effect on the earnings quality of consumer goods firms studied. Similarly, Agbaje et al. (2021) carried out a study on the effect of auditors' independence on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian deposit money banks from 2013 to 2018. The results of this study revealed that the audit fee has an insignificant impact on financial reporting quality.

Other studies found an inverse relationship between audit fees and earnings management. For example, Dijeh et al. (2022) investigated the association that exists between the audit attributes and the financial reporting quality of firms listed under the insurance sector of the Nigerian economy. The empirical result showed that the audit fee has an inverse statistical significant effect on financial reporting quality at 1% level. Bala et al. (2018) performed a study on audit

fees and the quality of financial reporting by listed firms in Nigeria. The study's research sample consists of 88 publicly listed Nigerian companies between 2012 and 2016. According to the study results, higher audit fees are associated with a lower level of discretionary accruals, and the combination of these characteristics predicts higher quality financial reporting.

In contrast, Mesbah and Ramadan (2022) examined the effect of audit quality on financial reporting quality. Earnings management and accounting conservatism are used as proxies for financial reporting quality. These variables were measured using secondary data obtained from the financial statements of 152 firms listed in the Egyptian stock market in the period from 2016 to 2020, representing 608 firm-year observations, excluding non-financial firms due to their special nature. Results provided evidence of a positive relationship between audit firm fees on one hand and financial reporting quality on the other. Osamuode (2022) examined auditor's independence and quality of financial report in the Nigeria public sector. This study used discretionary accruals as a proxy for the quality of financial reporting. The analysis results indicate that audit fees have a positive and significant relationship with auditors' independence. Owolabi and Afolayan (2020) researched auditor independence and financial reporting quality in listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study found that the independence of auditors and the accuracy of financial reporting in commercial banks are positively correlated. Otuya (2019) examined the relationship that exists between auditors' independence and the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria from 2013 through 2017. As methods of analysis, descriptive statistics and correlation statistics were used, and regressions were utilized to investigate the nature of the connection that exists between the variables that were the focus of the research. The findings of the research indicated that audit incentives had a strong positive link with the quality of financial reporting.

The review of literature showed that gaps exist in the literature. Prior studies argue that audit fees can be a significant factor for audit quality and thus enhance the financial reporting quality of firms. This is because audit fees is assumed to accelerate audit efforts, which is associated to greater audit coverage and thus leads to better financial reporting quality. While the determinants of audit fees are not new in literature, the significance of pricing audit fees within a bank's developing country context is limited. Therefore, this study examines how the audit fee paid by a firm affects the quality of the firm's financial report in commercial banks in Nigeria.

H₀₁: Auditors' fees have no significant positive effect on earnings management on banks in Nigeria.

Auditor tenure and earnings management

Adeyemi and Okpala (2015) defined audit tenure is the number of periods or years an audit firm, an auditor, audits a client or the number of years a company employs the same auditor. When an auditor has a long-term working connection with a client, that relationship may have an impact on the auditor's independence as well as the quality of the audit, which in turn can have an impact on the quality of the client's financial report (firm). According to Monroe and Hossain (2013), the mandatory rotation for an audit firm requires the firm to end the tenure

with its current auditor after a certain number of years. This rotation of the audit firm has both positive and negative impacts on financial reporting quality. Oyetunji et al. (2022) describe audit tenure as the long-term relationship that occurs between an auditor and a client. A long relationship between the auditor and the client may jeopardize the auditor's independence when familiarity and personal links develop, resulting in less vigilance on the side of the auditor, resulting in compromising or surrendering to management demands. Audit tenure has been dissected into large and short audit periods. Long audit tenure might decrease independence and professional care. On the other hand, a shorter audit tenure reflects that the auditors have less knowledge about the client, which may lead to low audit quality. Long audit tenure may increase the knowledge about the client's internal operations, but the downside is that the auditor's independence may be compromised. The clients change their auditors for many reasons, one of which is to obtain a reduced audit fee from a new auditor as the new auditor may offer services at a discount to win a new client. The auditor tenure may affect the quality of audits positively or negatively. Two arguments revolve around this issue: (Short tenure) which reflects that the auditor will lessen his experience in client's work, (Long period) meaning that the independence of auditor may decline. On the other hand, erosion in auditors' objectivity and independence due to the long relationships with the clients is perceived as the reason for a lower audit quality. In this study, auditor tenure is measured as the number of years the bank retained an auditor between 2012 and 2022.

Empirical studies such as Aondoakaa and Achika (2022); Dabor and Dabor (2015); Lambe et al., (2021); Okunola (2021); Otuya (2019); Oyebamiji (2022) auditor tenure has significantly affected earnings management. The findings of the research indicated that auditing tenure had a strong positive link with earnings management. According to the findings of the research, a longer auditor tenure and better incentives encourage independence of the auditor, which ultimately results in the detection of earnings management, which in turn improves the financial reporting quality. Meanwhile, Mesbah and Ramadan (2022); Olurankise and Ojo (2022) showed a negative relationship between audit firm tenure and financial reporting quality.

Dijeh et al. (2022); Ibrahim (2017); Olaoye et al. (2019); Olthof (2017); Onyabe et al. (2019); Osamuode (2022) examined auditor's independence and quality of financial report in the public sector in the year 2022. Longer audit tenure has an insignificant relationship with auditor independence. Debates on audit tenure arise from the assumption that the length of the relationship between the external auditor and the client may lead to an increase in earnings management by a company. This assumption is at the root of most of the debates on audit tenure. In this regard, the evidence presented in the previous research is mixed. Researches claimed that long auditor tenure negatively affects audit quality, weakens auditor's independence and objectivity, and lack of auditor's independence would encourage earnings management and creative accounting practices because due to longer auditor tenure, the auditors are closely linked to the management. Therefore, protect the stakes of management instead of stakeholders, whilst prior studies link long tenure of an audit firm to the independence of the auditor. This dichotomy calls for further research on audit tenure and earnings management.

H₀₂: Auditors' tenure has no significant positive effect on earnings management on banks in Nigeria.

Auditors' Status and Earnings Management

According to Otuya (2019), an auditor's status can be categorized in terms of an audit firm belonging to the Big Four audit firms such as KPMG, Ernst & Young, PwC and Akintola Williams Deloitte or non-Big Four which are other smaller audit firms. They argued that the Big Four audit firms have higher technical capability and have access to modern audit and accounting software and training that non-Big Four don't. The Big Four have the resources at their disposal to employ the best manpower and retain them. This is coupled with the fact that they also have an international presence and are able to move expertise and personnel to countries where certain proficiencies are deficient. Dijeh et al., (2022) described audit status as a situation of categorising external auditors into big four and non-big four audit firms. The big 4 audit firms are thought to be large audit firms with very large human and financial resources to prosecute any audit assignment given to it by the client. Because of the availability of resources to the big 4 audit firms against the non-Big 4 audit firms, literature had established link between the two variables. Ogungbade et al. (2021) defined audit status in binary form. Audit firms were categorized into Big four and Non-Big four. The Big Four, which includes KPMG, Pricewaterhouse Coopers (PWC), Ernst & Young(EY), and Deloitte, were coded "1" while other audit firms were coded "0".

Mesbah and Ramadan (2022) results provided evidence that financial statement users can trust the financial reports audited by Big 4 audit firms more than the financial reports audited by non-Big 4 audit firms. This provides implications for standard setters to focus more on the audit quality performed by non-Big 4 audit firms. On the contrary, the result of Dijeh et al. (2022) result indicated that audit type has an insignificant effect on financial reporting quality. The finding suggests that auditor status alone may not be a decisive factor in mitigating discretionary accruals. The auditor's capacity to identify or impact earnings management practices may be restricted by the particular intricacies and regulatory frameworks of the sector. Therefore, to guarantee high-quality financial reporting in banks, depending only on auditor status as a gauge of audit quality might not be enough.

Otuya (2019) examined the relationship that exists between auditors' independence and the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria. The Agency Theory served as the foundation for this investigation, and a content analysis research methodology was used for the study. The information included in the research was obtained from the annual reports of publicly traded manufacturing companies covering the years 2013 through 2017. As methods of analysis, descriptive statistics and correlation statistics were used, and regressions were utilized in order to investigate the nature of the connection that exists between the variables that were the focus of the research. The findings of the research indicated that auditing tenure had a strong positive link with quality of financial reporting. The study also discovered that auditor's status, such as being one of the big 4 audit firms, has a significant negative relationship with the quality of financial reporting. The Big 4 auditors such as Deloitte, PWC, KPMG, and EY over the years have earned a reputation in providing quality audit services and are expected to perform a high-

quality audit coherently to avoid audit failure because these firms will be on a high risk, losing clients as well as high audit fees. Various studies agreed that big 4 auditors are considered to providing a higher audit quality than non-big four auditors. Some researchers argue that when risk of detecting earnings management increases, then firms are more inclined to adopt less detectable earnings management strategy. Therefore, it is expected that firms audited by big4 auditors are likely to get less involved in determining the extent of discretionary accruals. While others argue that the big 4 audit firms, has a significant negative relationship with earnings management. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the effect of big 4 audit firms on earnings management in commercial banks in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Auditors' status have no significant positive effect on earnings management on banks in Nigeria.

Firm Size and Earnings Management

The size of a firm has been identified as a significant factor in determining earnings management. Empirical studies such as Mordi and Ebiaghan (2022) firm size have a significant but negative influence on earnings management support this claim. Larger firms frequently incur higher expenses as a result of increased public, regulatory, and investor scrutiny. Larger firms may use income smoothing, a type of earnings management, to reduce these expenses and show steady financial performance. According to prior researchers (Ghofir & Yusuf, 2020; Dang et al. 2024), larger firms are more motivated than smaller ones to implement income smoothing since strong profitability can draw attention from the media and customers.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts *ex-post facto* research design. The source of data for this study is from secondary sources which were extracted from the annual financial statements of the listed commercial banks for the period 2012 to 2023. The secondary source is more appropriate because all information needed for the study are available in the banks' financial statements. The population consist of all listed commercial banks in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at December 2023. The total number of commercial banks listed in NGX as at December 2023 were 14. The study adopts panel regression as a tool for data analysis. This method is relevant to the study, and the data for the study is a balance panel data. It has the characteristics of both cross-sectional data and time series data. The panel data gives more informative data, more variability, less collinearity among variables, more degree of freedom and more efficiency. It can detect and measure the effects that cannot be observed in cross-sectional or time series data (Gujarati 2009). The analytical tool is sophisticated enough to handle the relationship between two or more variables in the panel data and has dominated empirical studies in the existing literature. Also, the technique is considered appropriate for the study when the data collected fulfills the regression classical assumption assumptions; Normality of residual (residual plot) – Shapiro or Jarque-Bera, Linearity (Non – Linearity check), Homoscedasticity (hettest), Independence (Durbin Watson) for time series or macro panel and absence of multicollinearity (VIF).

Model Specification and Variable Measurement

The panel regression model that captures the effect of auditors independence on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria is presented below:

$$DACC_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 AT_{it} + \beta_2 B4_{it} + \beta_3 AF_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where,

DACC – Discretionary Accruals

AT – Auditors tenure

Big4 – auditors status Big 4

AF – Auditors fee

$\beta_1 \beta_3$ – Beta coefficient

α – constant

ε – error terms

it – identifier and time

Discretionary Accruals will be measured using the modified Jones model (Dechow et al.,1995) which is a three steps calculation procedure as illustrated below;

Total Accruals (TACC) = Discretionary accruals (DACC) + Non-discretionary accruals (NDA). For the modified Jones model we need to estimate discretionary accruals by subtracting NDA from TACC.

Step 1;

$$TACC_t = \text{Net income} - \text{Net operating cash flow}$$

Step 2;

$$NDA_t = \alpha_1(1/A_{t-1}) + \alpha_2[(\Delta REC_t - \Delta REC_t) / TA_{t-1}] + \alpha_3(PPE_t / TA_{t-1})$$

Step 3;

$$DACC_t = (TACC_t / TA_{t-1}) - [\alpha_1(1/TA_{t-1}) + \alpha_2[(\Delta REC_t - \Delta REC_t) / TA_{t-1}] + \alpha_3(PPE_t / TA_{t-1})]$$

Where;

$TACC_t$ is the Total Accruals in year t

$DACC_t$ is the Discretionary Accruals in year t

TA_{t-1} is the Total Assets in year t – 1

ΔREC_t is the Receivables in year t minus receivables in year t – 1

PPE_t is the Gross property plant and equipment in year t

$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ are the parameters to be estimated, namely alphas

Table 1: Description of Variables

Variables	Type	Description
Discretionary Accrual	Dependent variable	Discretionary accrual is measured using the Modified Jones Model
Auditors tenure	Independent variable	Measured as the number of years the bank retained an auditor between 2012 and 2022.
Auditors status (big 4)	Independent variable	If the audit firm of the bank is one of the big 4 or not
Auditors fee	Independent variable	Measured as the amount paid to the auditor as audit fee
Firm size	Control variable	Measured as the log of total asset

Authors compilation (2025)

4. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics shows the nature of each variable in this study. The results of descriptive analysis for these variables employed are presented in table 2

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
DACC	99	3405.46	2.39e+07	-8.47e+07	1.71e+08
Audten	100	3.9	2.504541	1	9
Audfee	100	1000879.7	167621.9	12	645000
Austatus	100	.99	.1	0	1
Firmsize	100	7.58e+08	1.61e+09	72508	9.66e+09

Stata Output (2025)

From table 2, it is observed that the average discretionary accruals value is N340,546,000.00 which implies that on the average, the management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria manipulates the financial report of the company through earnings management practices in order to make the financial statement look more attractive to investors with a deviation of N239,000,000.00. The table also shows the minimum and maximum DACC which implies that the minimum amount of earnings that has been manipulated by the management of the listed commercial banks is N847,000,000.00 and the maximum amount of earnings that has been manipulated is N1,710,000,000.00. The average auditor's tenure is approximately 4 years with a standard deviation of 2yrs, 5months. A listed commercial bank retained an auditor for the minimum of 1 year and the maximum number of years a bank retained an auditor is 9years. The result from table 1 also shows that the average fee paid to an auditor as their audit fee is N100,879,700.00 with a minimum fee of N12,000,000.00 and a maximum fee of N645,000,000.00. The average firm size based on the value of their total assets is N758,000,000,000 with a deviation of 1,610,000,000.00. The minimum firm size has a total asset of N725,080,000.00 and a maximum of N966,000,000,000.

Correlation Matrix

The pairwise correlation matrix was carried out in order to establish the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Table 3 shows the summary of the result.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	DAcc	Audten	Audfee	Austatus	Firmsize
DAcc	1.0000				
Audten	-0.0380	1.0000			
Audfee	-0.1336	0.3103	1.0000		
Austatus	0.0305	0.1170	-0.0115	1.0000	
Firmsize	-0.0259	0.3355	0.9211	0.0111	1.0000
VIF		1.14	6.61	1.02	6.72
Mean VIF	3.87				

Stata Output (2025)

The result from table 3 shows that there is a negative significant relationship between earnings management (discretionary accruals) and audit tenure. This implies that long audit tenure has a negative impact on earnings management in the firm’s financial report. Therefore, if a firm keeps an auditor for a long period of time, the management of the firm has a higher chance of manipulating the financial report using earnings management practices. Also, there is a negative significant relationship between audit fee and earnings management. This also implies that audit fee does not have any effect on earnings management. In contrast, there is a positive relationship between auditor’s status and earnings management. This implies that the status of the audit firm (whether the audit firm is one of the Big 4) affects the earnings management (discretionary accruals) in the firm’s financial report. Furthermore, table 2 shows that the size of the firm has a negative significant relationship with earnings management. This means that the size of a firm does not have any effect on earnings management of the firm. The residual of the regression analysis was subjected to a multicollinearity test to detect the presence of collinearity among the variables. The result shows that the mean of the variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was 3.87, which is lower than the threshold of 10. The VIF of individual variables was also lower than the threshold. This indicates that the explanatory variable included in the model were not correlated with one another thereby indicating an absence of multicollinearity between the variables.

Test of Hypothesis

Table 4: Fixed Effect Panel Regression Result

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t	P> t
Audfees	-241.9732	58.51709	-4.14	0.000
Audten	85102.04	1093725	0.08	0.938
Audstatus	15811.5	2.48e+07	0.00	0.999
Firmsize	.0179377	.0048099	3.73	0.000
R ² = 23%				
F-statistics	4.43			0.002
Hausman	1.11			0.022
Hetest	5.11			0.0237

Source: Stata Output (2025)

The result of the analysis in table 4 shows the regression coefficient (R²) which explains that 23% of the variations in the use of earnings management (discretionary accruals) practices to

improve the quality of the financial report can be explained by auditors' independence (auditors' tenure, audit fee, auditors' status and firm size). The F-statistics test was used to show the fitness of the model. The findings indicate that the F-statistics is statistically significant at 5%. Thus, it can be concluded that the model is fit to explain the effect of auditors' independence on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Hausman test was used to determine the fixed and random effects. Based on the outcome of the Hausman test, the fixed effect was found to be suitable for this study which was evident by the p-value ($P > 0.05$)

H₀₁: Audit fee has no significant effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Table 4 shows the panel regression result of audit fee on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. According to the findings, audit fee has a negative significant effect on earnings management which is revealed by the p-value ($P = 0.000$). Therefore this study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that audit fee has a significant effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This findings implies that Auditors are more inclined to devote more efforts to carrying out a comprehensive audit when banks pay higher audit fees. This lowers the possibility of earnings management through discretionary accruals and enhances the quality of financial reporting. A well-paid auditor is more motivated and equipped to examine financial accounts closely, making sure that management isn't manipulating accruals to inflate profits. This finding supports the study carried out by Dijeh et al. (2022) who concluded that audit fee has an inverse statistically significant effect on financial reporting quality. On the other hand, Agbaje et al. (2021) and Ibrahim (2017) in their study concluded that audit fee has no significant effect on earnings management of the firm studied.

H₀₂: Auditor's tenure has no significant effect on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

The panel regression result in table 4 shows that auditor's tenure has a positive and insignificant effect on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Based on this result, this study therefore accepts the null hypothesis which states that auditor's tenure has no significant effect on the performance of listed commercial banks in Nigeria at 5% level of significance ($P = 0.08$). This finding implies that an increase in auditor's tenure will have no effect on discretionary accruals. The conclusion made on the findings implies that, an increase or decrease in the number of years an auditor audits the account of the bank does not necessarily increase or decrease the chances of management manipulating the financial report of the bank using earnings management practices. In other words, the auditor's tenure does not affect discretionary accruals in the firm's financial report. This finding does not support the agency theory, which argued that conflicts exist between the principal and agents when the agents fail to protect the interest of the shareholders by increasing financial performance. This finding is in line with the findings from the research carried out by Onyabe et al., (2018), Osamuade (2022) which concluded that longer audit tenure has a positive but insignificant effect on discretionary accruals. This finding, however, is in contrast with Aondoakaa and Achika (2022)

who found out that audit tenure has a significant effect with earnings management. In the same vein, Lambe et al. (2021) also concluded based on their findings that audit tenure has a significantly positive effect on discretionary accruals.

H₀₃: Auditors' status has no significant effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria.

Table 4 also reveals the panel regression result of auditor's status and earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. According to the analysis, it was found that the p-value was positive and insignificant as revealed by the p-value ($P = 0.999$). Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis, which states that auditors' status has no significant effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This implies that auditor's status (whether the auditor is one of the big four audit firms or not) has no significant effect on discretionary accruals in listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This suggests that, despite the reputation and resources associated with larger audit firms, their involvement does not necessarily curtail earnings management practices in the banking sector. Agbage et al. (2021) study on banks revealed an insignificant impact. This further supports the notion that the status of the auditor does not necessarily influence the level of discretionary accruals within banks. On the other hand, Otuya (2019) was of the conclusion that auditor's status has a significant negative relationship with the quality of financial reporting proxied by discretionary accruals.

A control variable was introduced in the model, which is the firm size measured as a log of total assets. Table 4 shows that firm size has a positive and significant effect on discretionary accruals as revealed by the p-value ($P = 0.00$). This implies that the larger firm has an effect on discretionary accruals in the financial report of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. This implies that larger banks in Nigeria use discretionary accrual to manipulate its profit than smaller banks.

Heteroscedasticity Test

One of the statistical assumptions of regression analysis is that the error terms for all observations have a common variance (homoscedastic). On the contrary, varying variance errors are said to be heteroscedastic. The heteroscedasticity was tested in the residuals of the estimations using the Breusch-Pagan/ Cook-Weisberg test. The null hypothesis is stated thus: there is no heteroscedasticity. From the analysis, the model had no heteroscedasticity. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis was accepted because it was found to be significant at 2%, which led to the application of Hausman's test.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the effect of auditors' independence on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the effect of auditor's tenure, audit fee and auditor's status on earnings management of listed commercial banks in Nigeria from 2012 to 2023. The secondary data were analysed using descriptive statistics and a correlation matrix. The hypotheses were tested using fixed panel regression. The result shows that the audit fee has a significant negative effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial

banks in Nigeria. Auditor's tenure and status have an insignificant effect on discretionary accruals of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions are made: Higher auditor fees typically result in fewer discretionary accruals in banks due to improved audit quality, higher auditor vigilance, and regulatory compliance. This partnership promotes financial transparency and stability in the banking system. The finding suggests that mandatory audit firm tenure policies may not be necessary if other mechanisms, such as robust regulatory environments, auditor specialization, and effective audit committees, are in place to ensure audit quality. Focusing on these factors may be more effective in enhancing financial reporting quality than solely limiting auditor tenure. The finding suggest that, in the context of banks, auditor status alone may not be a decisive factor in mitigating discretionary accruals. This could be due to the unique complexities and regulatory environments of the banking industry, which might limit the auditor's ability to detect or influence earnings management practices. Therefore, relying solely on auditor status as a measure of audit quality may not be sufficient to ensure high-quality financial reporting in banks. The following recommendations are put forward:

- i. Banks should avoid paying too low audit costs, which could lower the quality of the audit, and instead pay prices that reflect the complexity of their financial processes. To keep audits successful, regulators should set baseline fees.
- ii. Regulators should focus on strengthening audit quality control measures rather than imposing strict tenure limits. Regular inspections and enforcement of ethical standards can mitigate risks associated with long auditor tenure.
- iii. Regulators should strengthen policies ensuring auditor independence, as auditor status alone may not constrain discretionary accruals. Measures such as mandatory audit firm rotation and restrictions on non-audit services can help mitigate potential conflicts of interest.

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